

Design and experimental validation of a filter-based allocation strategy for the longitudinal dynamics control in an autonomous motorcycle

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Abstract: Autonomous driving has expanded across various domains, with advancements in urban robo-taxis, autonomous delivery vehicles, agricultural applications, and racing competitions. However, autonomous technology for two-wheeled vehicles remains under-explored, with limited literature and industrial demonstrations. Despite motorcycles already feature basic autonomous components like cruise control, traction control, and anti-lock braking systems (ABS), full autonomy demands integrated control of front braking pressure and rear regenerative torque.

This work addresses the torque allocation problem inside the longitudinal dynamics control of an autonomous motorcycle, which is under development at Politecnico di Milano from a commercial fully-electric *Eva Ribelle*. In particular, a complementary filter-based dynamic allocation strategy is proposed to distribute braking forces effectively, considering actuator limits. After a simulation-based tuning to handle the trade-off between braking distance and vertical load transfer variations on the wheels, an experimental validation has been carried out on a test track. Experimental results confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Motorcycles, Torque Distribution, Longitudinal Dynamics Control, Autonomous Riding

1. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous driving has rapidly expanded across various scenarios in recent years. Urban applications (Yurtsever et al. (2020)), are at the forefront, leading advancements toward the commercialization of robo-taxis and autonomous delivery vehicles are being developed, ranging from small-scale models to heavy-duty transport solutions. The agricultural sector is also significantly employing this technology, leveraging its advantages in known, low-traffic environments, e.g., Roshanianfard et al. (2020). Lastly, autonomous driving faces a unique challenge developing high-speed solutions tested in autonomous racing competitions (Betz et al. (2022)). Despite its broad adoption, autonomous technologies for two-wheeled vehicles is still in its early stages. Current research is limited to simulation studies and a few practical demonstrations, e.g., Nenner et al. (2010), alongside some industrial showcases. However, motorcycles already incorporate elements of autonomy, such as cruise control, traction control (TC), e.g., Tanelli et al. (2009), and anti-lock braking systems (ABS), e.g., Huang and Shih (2010). In this study*, an autonomous motorcycle is being developed at Politecnico di Milano, Milan (MI), Italy, from the full-electric *Eva Ribelle* commercialized by Energica Motor Com-

pany, Modena (MO), Italy, shown in Fig. 1, as an extreme concept of Advanced Rider Assistance Systems (ARAS). The first phase involves designing a longitudinal dynamics controller, which, possibly, can be done by integrating concepts from cruise control, traction control, and ABS. While each of these systems traditionally regulates a single control variable – cruise and traction control adjust motor torque, and ABS controls front braking pressure –, autonomous riding demands simultaneous control of both front braking pressure and rear regenerative torque, calling for a torque allocation strategy. For motorcycles, this problem is low discussed in the current literature; examples can be found in Baumann et al. (2016) for cornering braking or in Lenzo and Lot (2024), for a particular all-wheel-drive electric motorcycle.

This study specifically addresses the torque allocation problem during braking phases, ensuring that the desired longitudinal force is satisfied by dynamically distributing it between rear-wheel regenerative torque and front-wheel braking pressure. The main contributions of this work are: 1) the design of a complementary filter-based dynamic allocation strategy, which takes actuator limitations into account; 2) a simulation-based tuning to handle the trade-off between minimizing braking distance and mitigating vertical load transfer variation between the wheels; 3) the experimental validation on a test track on straight, where results confirmed its validity and effectiveness.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the motorcycle prototype, the experimental setup, and the simulation environment. Section 3 gives an overview

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Fig. 1. Autonomous motorcycle prototype: a commercial *Eva Ribelle* equipped with additional control units, actuators and sensors.

of the longitudinal dynamics control and the defines the torque allocation problem. Finally, the allocation strategy is presented and tuned in Section 4, and experimentally validated in Section 5.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

In this section, the considered motorcycle prototype is presented, highlighting the additional control units, actuators and sensors. Then, the proving ground and the simulation scheme are described along with the considered testing maneuver.

2.1 Autonomous motorcycle prototype.

The autonomous motorcycle prototype is presented in Fig. 1 with some technical details provided below, focusing on the control units, actuators and sensors utilized for this work.

Control unit. A Speedgoat by Mathworks, Portola Valley, CA, USA, is installed on the vehicle as the real-time Vehicle Dynamics Control Unit (VDCU). It communicates via a Controller Area Network (CAN) with the necessary actuators and sensing control units.

Actuators. To control the longitudinal dynamics, both traction and braking torque need to be actuated. The built-in Vehicle Control Unit (VCU) software has been modified to accept an external torque command coming via CAN from the the VDCU. This allows traction and braking torque to be delivered on the rear-wheel by the electric motor. However, due to torque limitations in braking phases, an additional brake-by-wire (BBW) actuator by Brembo Racing, Curno (BG), Italy, is installed on the front wheel, which is managed by its own control unit to actuated a pressure reference, as in Radrizzani et al. (2020).

Sensors. At this stage, required information is obtained from both commercial and additional sensors mounted on the prototype. Specifically:

- wheel speeds are measured by the built-in encoders;
- motor torque is computed by the VCU from electric motor current measurements;
- the BBW provided feedback on the actuated pressure;
- an analog sensing unit (ASU) has been added to publish the front and rear suspension elongation on the CAN bus, measured by additional analog linear potentiometers;
- a 6-axis inertial measurement unit (IMU), i.e., the e-Lean by e-Shock, Milan (MI), Italy, gives the linear and angular accelerations of the chassis;

- an optical sensing unit (OSU) by Kistler, Winterthur, Switzerland, is mounted on the underside of the vehicle to measure the real longitudinal and lateral speed. It also provides an estimate of motorcycle roll and pitch angels.

2.2 Proving ground.

The experimental validation of this work was conducted at the track at CREA, Treviglio (BG), Italy, which revealed particularly useful for preliminary testing. As depicted in Fig. 2, the track features two straight segments, with 65 km/h as speed limit, linked by two ground curved road sections.

Fig. 2. CREA track in Treviglio (BG), Italy.

2.3 Simulation environment.

To design and tune control strategies, a simulation environment has been employed before starting an experimental campaign, as detailed in Section 5. Specifically, Vi-BikeRealTime, a commercial high-fidelity multi-body simulator developed by Vi-Grade, Tavagnacco (UD), Italy, has been integrated with the VDCU code in the Simulink environment by Mathworks, as depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Simulation environment.

2.4 Testing maneuver.

Given the aim of this work, a hard braking on straight from 60 to 30 km/h has been designed as testing maneuver, so to be compliant with the track limits. Hence, the test is governed by two trigger buttons, one sets the target speed to 60 km/h, the other one to 30 km/h.

3. LONGITUDINAL DYNAMICS CONTROL AND PROBLEM DEFINITION

The longitudinal dynamics control can be effectively managed using a modular approach. First, a speed controller calculates the total torque T_{tot} required to maintain the speed target v^* . Next, an allocation strategy determines how to distribute the total torque between the front braking torque T_b , constrained by $\underline{T}_b < T_b < 0$, and the rear motor torque T_m , bounded by $\underline{T}_m < T_m < \bar{T}_m$. subsequently, these torques are converted into

Fig. 4. Test setup: reference and measure speed (top), and triggers (bottom).

a braking pressure reference p_b^* for the BBW and a throttle command θ_m^* for the VCU. Furthermore, TC or ABS can be introduced to adjust the throttle and pressure references, respectively, to keep the wheel slip inside safe limits. The resulting control scheme is illustrated in Fig. 5.

For the purposes of this study, the speed controller is implemented as a proportional-integral (PI) control strategy, augmented with vehicle drag compensation, that closes the loop with a bandwidth of 0.5 Hz. Then, TC and ABS are deactivated. Finally, the design and implementation of the torque allocation strategy form the core objective and contribution of this work. Before delving into its details, the torque allocation problem is outlined.

Fig. 5. Longitudinal dynamics control scheme.

In vehicles – particularly two-wheeled ones – effective torque distribution between the front and rear wheels is critical, as emphasized in Corno et al. (2008). During acceleration, torque is typically delivered solely through the rear wheel. However, during braking, longitudinal forces can be applied by both the front and rear wheels. To highlight the consequences of actuation on the rear or front wheel, some simulated examples are presented and analyzed.

Fig. 6 illustrates the differences observed simulating the braking phase of the test shown in Fig. 4, comparing two scenarios: when the braking torque is applied solely to the rear wheel at the maximum regenerative torque ($T_m = -45$ Nm) and when it is applied solely to the front wheel, under varying values of maximum braking pressure \bar{p}_b associated with different maximum braking torques T_b . It can be observed that increasing the braking pressure on the front wheel allows for a higher longitudinal force and, consequently, greater deceleration compared to relying solely on the rear motor maximum regenerative torque. Important to highlight is that also actuating the same value of torque but on the front instead of the rear generates

Fig. 6. Comparison between braking solely on the rear wheel at the maximum regenerative torque ($T_m = -45$ Nm) and solely on the front wheel, under varying values of maximum braking torques T_b .

Fig. 7. Comparison between braking solely on the rear wheel at the maximum regenerative torque ($T_m = -45$ Nm) and combined on the front wheel, under varying values of maximum braking torques T_b .

a higher longitudinal torque and so deceleration. This is due to the vertical load transfer from the rear to the front during braking (Cossalter et al. (2000)), highlighting the importance of an allocation strategy of the torque applied on each wheel. The load transfer can be defined using a normalized index, i.e., the ratio between the vertical load on the front and the total vertical load.

Furthermore, the effects become more pronounced when braking force is applied to both wheels, enhancing overall braking performance. As shown in Fig. 7, where the maximum regenerative torque is applied to the rear wheel and varying levels of maximum braking pressure are applied to the front one, it is evident that higher longitudinal torque results in increased wheel slip due to the reduction in vertical load on the rear. Generally, achieving the same braking performance with higher slip poses safety risks (Corno et al. (2008)) and accelerates wear (Radrizzani et al. (2024)). Additionally, in the most aggressive scenario, the phenomenon known as a *stoppie* – where the rear

Fig. 8. Correlation between load transfer rate and pitch rate.

wheel lifts off the ground – can be observed when the load transfer index is equal to 1. It is also visible that the transient is a riskier situation with respect to steady-state due overshoots in the load transfer and slip dynamics.

This situation, along with the effects on the slip motivate the critical importance of implementing a torque allocation strategy, which should handle the trade-off between braking performance and load unbalance.

However, since directly measuring the actual load transfer is challenging, related variables are identified to facilitate an effective experimental analysis. Notably, Fig. 8 reveals a strong correlation between the pitch rate and the difference in load transfer rate. Therefore, the pitch rate is selected as the measurable quantity to represent how fast the load transfer changes moving towards possible risky situations, particularly in transients.

4. ALLOCATION STRATEGY: DESIGN AND TUNING

To handle the trade-off between pitch rate and braking performance, the proposed allocation strategy is based on a complementary filter approach, which also accounts for the limits of each actuator. As visible in Fig. 9, the total torque T_{tot} coming from the speed controller is entirely allocated to the electric motor not only in traction but also for small braking torque requests, i.e., lower than εT_m , in order to avoid small and quick activations of the BBW. The low-pass filter is designed as a first-order dynamical system with α_{lp} as gain and f_{lp} as cut-off frequency, expressed in Hz. For its effective employment in the allocation strategy, two important features should be implemented: • it must filter just when the braking torque is increasing (i.e., for negative values of the braking torque rate) to allow fast brakes release and avoid sign mismatches between the rear and front torques; • it must consider the actuator limits.

- The first one is realized starting from the continuous-time t

Fig. 9. Allocation strategy based on the complementary-filter principle.

Fig. 10. Input-saturated (a) and state-saturated (b) structures of the low-pass filters, where z represent the variable of the Z-transform.

version of a generic low-pass filter subsequently converted into a discrete-time k filter with the Euler method:

$$x(k) = \begin{cases} x(k-1) + 2\pi f_{\text{lp}} T_s (u(k) - x(k)), & \beta_{\text{lp}}(k) = 1 \\ u(k), & \beta_{\text{lp}}(k) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$y(k) = \alpha_{\text{lp}} x(k) \quad (2)$$

where u is the input of the filter, x the state and y output, and T_s is the sampling time. Finally, $\beta_{\text{lp}}(k)$ is a time-varying boolean variable defined as:

$$\beta_{\text{lp}}(k) = \begin{cases} 0, & u(k) - x(k) \geq 0 \\ 1, & u(k) - x(k) < 0 \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

i.e., it is equal to one just when the rate of the filter is negative.

- To constrain the signal in $[u, \bar{u}]$, saturation is introduced. Since a saturation is a non-linear element, a different location produces different results, so, two alternatives are considered. In the first one, the saturation is on the input u ; in the second one, on the state x . These two solutions have been named the input-saturated low-pass filter and the state-saturated low-pass filter, respectively. They are shown in Fig. 10. Therefore, the structure of the filter becomes a design parameter along with its gain α_{lp} and cut-off frequency f_{lp} .

Finally, referring to the hierarchical scheme in Fig. 5, it is worth to mention that the proposed allocation strategy may not apply the total torque requested by the higher-level speed controller. Consequently, the anti-windup strategy of the PI-based speed controller is adapted, as depicted in Fig. 11, by monitoring the difference between the requested torque and the allocated torque to determine whether to clamp the integral action.

Fig. 11. Speed control anti-windup strategy integration with the allocation strategy.

Fig. 12. Pareto-like curves as a function of the filter structure and cut-off frequency.

Fig. 13. Time-domain comparison of the speed, torque and pitch rate for different filter structures and cut-off frequencies.

The tuning of the design parameters is now detailed through simulations in Section 4.1 and experimentally validated in Section 4.2.

4.1 Filter structure selection.

The structure of the low-pass filter is selected from the two alternatives previously shown in Fig. 10. This selection is made by simulating the maneuver depicted in Fig. 4 for each alternative, using various values of the cut-off frequency f_{lp} while keeping the filter gain fixed at $\alpha_{lp} = 1$. The results, summarized for both filter architectures in Fig. 12, show the trade-off between minimizing braking distance and the highest absolute pitch rate as a function of f_{lp} . It is evident that the state-saturated filter is consistently better than the input-saturated option, as its Pareto front is always positioned lower.

To gain insight into the motivations behind these results, we can examine Fig. 13. The state-saturated strategy, tuned to 0.5 Hz as a balanced compromise between two conflicting objectives, is compared with the input-saturated strategy. The latter is analyzed at 0.5 Hz, where it shares the same maximum pitch rate but achieves lower performance, and at 1 Hz, where it exhibits the opposite characteristics. The increased braking distance of the input-saturated filter tuned to 0.5 Hz results from

Fig. 14. Pareto-like curves as a function of the filter gain and cut-off frequency.

Fig. 15. Time-domain comparison of the speed, torque and load transfer for different filter cut-off frequencies.

a lower total torque applied during the transient, characterized by slower variations and, consequently, a reduced pitch rate. Conversely, the similar total torque behavior observed with the state-saturated option at 0.5 Hz and the input-saturated filter at 1 Hz leads to the same braking distance. However, the input-saturated filter at 1 Hz achieves a higher peak pitch rate due to a faster variation in the total torque.

4.2 Filter parameters tuning.

Since no benefits have been observed with the input-saturated architecture, the filter parameter tuning is exclusively performed for the state-saturated one. The methodology outlined in Section 4.1 is again followed, but with a lower total braking torque limit, in order to guarantee that, despite of different tuning of α_{lp} , the same total braking torque can be reached at steady-state. Results are summarized in the Pareto-like curves in Fig. 14, which show that the optimal tuning consistently occurs with $\alpha_{lp} = 1$, indicating that, in steady-state conditions, the full braking potential of the front is utilized. Conversely, the cut-off frequency becomes the critical parameter in balancing the trade-off between minimizing braking distance (favored by higher values) and minimizing pitch rate (favored by lower values). A well-balanced compromise is achieved with cut-off

frequency values around 0.5 Hz, as demonstrated in Fig. 15, for two primary reasons. • Setting the cut-off frequency to 0.5 Hz results in a slower variation of the total braking torque, which effectively reduces the load transfer peaks observed during transients. • The steady-state braking torque is achievable at this frequency, ensuring that there are no notable impacts on speed behavior. In contrast, lower cut-off frequency values prevent the steady-state braking torque from being reached.

5. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The experimental validation is conducted at the proving ground presented in Section 2.2 aiming at replicating the results obtained during the simulation tuning of the filter cut-off frequency. Indeed, thanks to the previous analysis, the structure of the filter has been fixed to the state-saturated architecture and the filter gain has been set to $\alpha_p = 1$.

Results are represented in Fig. 16 showing a Pareto-like curve, as expected by previous simulations. The experimental points used to shape Fig. 16 are obtained by averaging multiple repetitions of the same test, described in Section 2.4, to reduce noise. The repeatability of each test is visualized in Fig. 17, where the same vehicle speed, used to compute the braking distance, and the pitch rate are shown for each test along with the computed average. It is worth to mention that both the speed and the pitch rate are returned by the optical sensing unit mentioned in Section 2. Finally, recalling the relationship between the pitch rate and the load transfer rate shown in Fig. 8, the pitch rate reduction makes the motorcycle more stable and controllable in braking phases.

Fig. 16. Experimental Pareto-like curve as a function of the cut-off frequency.

Experimental results confirmed the outcome of simulation shown in Fig. 12 and 14: low frequencies are associated to a slow pitch rate and low braking performance; opposite, high frequencies generate a faster braking but reach a faster pitch rate. Therefore, 0.5 Hz represent a suitable compromise, because with a slightly longer braking (+7%), the pitch rate is significantly reduced (-45%).

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work addressed the torque allocation problem inside the longitudinal dynamics control of an autonomous motorcycle. The proposed dynamic allocation approach, after a simulation-based tuning, has been experimentally validated on a proving ground, confirming its capability of handling the trade-off between braking distance and vertical load balance on the wheel. As future works, it will be benchmarked with optimization-based approaches and tested in different tracks and conditions.

Fig. 17. Experimental time-domain comparison of the speed and pitch rate for different filter cut-off frequencies (different colors), and bold lines represent the average value.

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